

A STUDY ON QULAITY OF WORK LIFE OF THE SRI RENGA APPERALS, COIMBATORE

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ABSTRACT

Quality of life means that the level of happiness or dissatisfaction on one's career. Quality is no more a specialized word but has become necessary and the greatest asset to any organization. Maintaining and managing the quality of such human aspects is through the maintenance of quality of work perfectly. The high QWL gives the better result in the organization performance, effectiveness, innovativeness etc. It is the corroboration between the employees and their organization. It helps to increase the family life and work life of the individuals. The factors that determine the QWL are attitude, environment, opportunities ,nature of job, stress level, challenges, growth and development and risk involved in work and reward.

Keywords: Quality of work life, Organization commitment and job security.

INTRODUCTION

Quality of work life is the set of organizational conditions. This phrase is used with frequency to describe the environmental and humanistic values. It can be said to be all the original inputs which aim at improving the employee's satisfaction and enhancing organizational effectiveness. It becomes mandatory for all the organizations. Business organizations attention is

focused on the quality of human experience in the work place. Implementation of procedures and policies make the work less routine and more rewarding for the employees which includes autonomy, recognition, belongingness, development and external rewards.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Radha and Ishu (2015), in their study "Employees satisfaction on quality of work life at state bank of India", is of the opinion that, the quality of work life is becoming an complicated issue to achieve the objectives of the organization in every sector. It is a link between the employees and their organization.

Shefali and Rooma (2014), "A study on quality of work life: key elements and its implication" says that identifying the elements to measure the quality of work life is a difficult task. The high degree of QWL leads to job satisfaction which ultimately results in effective and efficient performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The universe of the study comprises of employees from Sri Renga Textile And Companies. A sample of 120 employees of various departments are selected as respondents on the basis of convenience sampling method. The primary data is collected through questionnaire and secondary data through the journals and websites. To evaluate the quality of work life among the employees, the opinion of respondents is put under 5 point scale. The questionnaire is used for assessing the employees satisfaction level and job security

RESULT AND INTERPRETATION

It deals with the findings related to the respondents perception towards the various parameters regarding quality of work life of the employees.

TABLE: 1**Perception of respondents towards various parameters regarding quality of work life**

S. No.	Factors (Highly satisfied,satisfied,neutral,Dissatisfied, Highly dissatisfied)	MEAN SCORE
1	Opinion on working environment	3.84
2	Leave facilities	3.33
3	Job security	3.62
4	Career growth	3.21
5	Health and safety measures	3.69
6	Workload	4.31
7	Freedom in work	2.44
8	Job satisfaction	4.12
9	Training programs to employees	2.59
10	Co-ordination and co-operation with workers	4.59
11	Workers participation improve quality of work life	4.12
12	Affects productivity	3.38
13	Promotion policies	2.10

The above table shows that the factors that obtained highly satisfied mean score are like co-ordination and co-operation with workers(4.59),workload (4.31), job satisfaction(4.12), work participation Improve quality of work life (4.12).Most of the respondents satisfied with working environment, leave facilities, job security, career growth, health and safety measures and quality of work life affects productivity. The lowest factor is (2.10) promotion polices for highly dissatisfied.

TABLE : 2

MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS

FACTORS	RESPONDENTS	RANK
WORK INTEREST	45	1
RECOGNITION	11	4
REWARDS	18	3
COMPENSATION	36	2
FRIENDLY WITH WORKERS	10	5

The above table shows that most are satisfied with the interesting work and compensation. They are least satisfied with the friendly with workers

FINDINGS

- 4.59 (MEAN SCORE) of the respondents are highly satisfied with the co-ordination and co-operation with the workers
- 4.12 (MEAN SCORE) of the respondents strongly agreed that they have job satisfaction.
- 91% of the respondents are satisfied for overall satisfaction of employee welfare activities in the Organization.

SUGGESTION

The company should focus on addressing the employees about their policies, guide and support on situations when they need help of subordinates and provide basic necessities such as quality food, water and sanitary equipments.

CONCLUSION

From the study it is concluded that quality of work life contribute to the workers performance in a holistic manner. It also helps to know how the workers are treated by the management. As a whole it helps to develop the human resources by improving the quality of life.

REFERENCE

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